

An Expensive Luxury? Conserving the JW Evans Silverware Factory

At first glance, JW Evans, Silverware Factory, appears to be an unprepossessing group of houses amongst other accommodation. However, behind these four Victorian terraced houses is a treasure trove of drop stamps, presses, furnaces, tools, archives and records from over 120 years of a manufacturing silverware factory. Located in Birmingham's jewellery quarter in the West Midlands, it was a family owned and operated business designing and manufacturing silver tableware components. The completeness of the business, the minutiae of manufacturing and its unique ambiance made clear that this was an incredibly important property 'one of the most complete surviving examples of a Jewellery Quarter'.

The Birmingham Jewellery Quarter is Europe's largest concentration of businesses involved in the jewellery trade and still produces approximately 40% of all the jewellery made in the UK. However it is a shadow of its former self; at its peak in the 1900s over 30,000 people were employed within the Quarter and its trade the most lucrative in the city. The demand for products peaked in 1920, after this the Great Depression marked the start of a steady decline. During the World Wars manufacturing turned to munitions but decline continued, mainly due to cheaper foreign competition. In the twenty years between 1965 and 1985 employment figures fell from approximately 8,000 people in 900 firms to 4,000 people in 600 firms.

JW Evans traded continuously from its founding in 1881 until its sale to English Heritage in 2008. Despite years with no profits, the owner was unwilling to sell the Grade II* property for redevelopment. English Heritage already had had an involvement in supporting initiatives in the Jewellery Quarter, such as awarding grants to maintain historic buildings and by undertaking a survey of the entire Jewellery Quarter in 1998. The building and contents were in a very poor state and significant investment was required for the site to be sustainable, as either a business or heritage attraction. Other organisations considered acquiring JW Evans, but found it economically unviable. With the very real danger of the properties and contents being lost, English Heritage bought the business in March 2008, including all the archives, silver from the showroom and machinery. The previous owner, Tony Evans was retained as consultant to advise us with his fund of knowledge (as well as to record his memories).

A plan of action and Conservation Philosophy was required. It was decided that the 'spirit of place' was the single most important aspect of the site and minimal intervention the objective for the project. As well as preserving the special atmosphere there was the need to preserve important information relating to the processes and activities within the silverware factory. The rooms often showed evidence of changes from their original use as residential spaces then being subsumed for industry and the final slide into neglect and disuse as the business became smaller and less prosperous. The amount of patina and dust on the tools often indicated their purpose and the frequency of

their usage. The contents were significant because they were complete but also in context (and in some cases had been so for over 50 years). It was these associations and wealth of inter-related information that might have been lost by a simple inventory and 'tidying up' without a full understanding of the property and contents.

It was decided that it was both ethically and practically achievable to retain the collection in situ through minimal intervention or 'conserve as found'. To take this to its ultimate conclusion would be to do nothing and allow the stately slide into deterioration to accelerate – already a recent theft of lead from the roof was causing widespread water ingress. The initial strategic discussions defined where to stop and how to achieve a compromise between preservation and 'spirit of place'? Importantly the team also had to consider whether financially this could be achieved both during the works and in relation to future maintenance.

Typically, a project of this scale would start with intensive inventory recording, before packing and decanting the contents. In this instance, almost uniquely, the majority of the c. 52,000 objects were protected in situ and, as on an archaeological site, fully recorded only if the surrounding works required their displacement. Only in rare instances were the objects accessioned, such as the showroom silverware which had already been relocated from number 52 Albion Street which had been sold by Tony Evans in 2005. Undertaking a comprehensive recording of the objects would, in many cases have necessitated disturbing objects and cleaning them to be able to identify them or differentiate between them (the reverse of minimal intervention).

To give a comparison, some of the costs incurred in a current project to relocate stored museum collections can be used. The comparison project involved the documentation, repacking and movement of five storage units containing approximately 125,000 objects in the West Midlands. The collection is much larger but a large amount of documentation and packing has already occurred. To carry out this work has taken approximately two years and involved over 10 staff (both part and full time). A unit a little over 10,000 square feet (so large enough to potentially store all the contents) has a cost of £38,000 per annum (not counting services etc), whilst packing materials and crates have been approximately another £20,000. There would also be additional costs for transportation as well as staff contractors and staff (not to mention those already on staff who have been seconded onto the project) resulting in a cost of approximately half the total costs for the Phase I of the JW Evans project.

A survey and assessment was carried out for both the building and collections within. Quantifying the number of objects on site and gaining an overview of the main risk factors for the different types of collections was essential as it had already been acknowledged that neither the condition of the objects nor the environment they were housed in was ideal. The principle aim of the assessment was to quantify the risks actually causing damage; the metal items were dusty, dirty and often corroded; but it was not confirmed that this corrosion was active. As well as influencing initial project and building works, the audit has been used to justify and cost continuing works required to the collection.

It was also agreed that in order to keep the majority of the collections in situ during building works a conservator must be at the heart of the project working full-time onsite with the design and construction team. The conservator (the author) would be based on site to oversee the works and prevent damage to the historic fabric and collections. The early and continuous involvement of a conservator meant that it was possible to troubleshoot issues early by allocating sufficient time and resources. At a cost of one full time conservator the project also gained other advantages, with them taking on many of 'clerk of works' duties ensuring English Heritage always had a representative on site so that any queries could be dealt with in a timely manner to avoid expensive hold ups.

The scope of works and resulting budget made the project more practical to split over two years. For Phase I, a budget of £750K was committed (which included a £113K grant from Birmingham City Council). The external works were extensive; a new roof over all four houses and workshops as well as new roof lights and repaired chimneys. Guttering was renewed (and widened) and all windows and external doors repaired. There was also the added complication of needing to strengthen brick boundary walls in the workshops as they were only single four inch brick skin. Asbestos had been used extensively within the spaces and there were also a multitude of chemicals (many in unlabelled bottles) all of which had to be dealt with.

Although major works were required to achieve a weatherproof building, they had the potential for widespread damage to the interior collections. Much consideration was given to protecting the interiors of the rooms and their contents. There was a concern that the more common method of protection by 'boxing in' all the ferrous items and wooden shelving might cause an adverse microclimate in what was a very damp space which could accelerate mould and corrosion damage. If the items were concealed, monitoring their presence (for security) or further deterioration would also present problems. It was also acknowledged that it would be very hard to allow public access and engagement if everything was hidden for over a year. After much discussion and with the knowledge there would be an English Heritage conservator seconded to the project and on site throughout, a strategy was developed for each room by the conservator and architect. A system of protection criteria was specified and this key was then applied to different areas, for instance protection for stairs and hand rails would be 'Type G', boxed in with hardboard. The majority of materials used were widely available and relatively cheap and the structures, although individually made were as simple as possible.

An unusual part of this strategy was to install scaffolding platforms throughout each of the single storey workshops (where the roofs were to be renewed) without first protecting individual items. These access platforms would also be used as false ceilings, protecting the contents underneath from dust, debris or possible Asbestos contamination (as well as contractors!). The scaffold planks were then lined with several thicknesses of polythene and sealed around the edges with pipe lagging. Any items projecting above this level were individually covered over and also tightly sealed. Some individual items underneath the platforms also had further protection, such as soft wrapping

with Tyvek® or rigid boxes (some with viewing and ventilation panels) which were built to be sturdy enough to be stood upon.

The scaffolding strategy proved to be justified. As the roofs began to be stripped and worked upon, it became clear that the plaster and lathe ceilings were in worse condition than the survey had indicated. Large parts of the ceilings were loose and some fell down as works began, but the scaffolding stood up well to these surprises and kept the spaces below both clean and accessible. It also allowed work to continue as planned and to time. Had there only been individual or soft protection this would needed to have been increased before works could have continued.

A great deal of supervision was required during installation due to the spaces being very narrow, difficult to negotiate with long poles and crowded with objects (not to mention dealing with the machismo attitude of the scaffolders). This was all supervised by the conservator, and stipulations in the tendering stated that only one space could be scaffolded at a time to prevent rooms not being covered. Once in place, the platforms allowed the contractors to work freely above the rooms without being in contact with any contents.

With the completion of Phase I, attention turned to the internal works. The most pressing need was to renew the electrical system, install a fire system and extend the security system. As the site was not being 'tidied up' all existing defunct systems and wiring were left in place (in some cases there were several). A very conscientious electrician rewired through the existing old metal conduits and reused old switches, again minimising disruption to the ambience of the site. The electric motor in the Main Stamp Shop was overhauled but the external casing was left dirty and greasy to the bemusement of the engineers. This greatly added to the ambience, but was much slower than conventional rewiring (although a small amount of time was saved by not having to remove the previous rewiring and only cable tying in cables in some areas). Eventually, the cost of refurbishing the old motor was about the same price as it would have been to have bought a new, potentially more reliable machine.

It was agreed that the Main Stamp Shop should continue to function as a working Shop, (as this was the main area which had been used right up to the time of sale). As well as servicing the motor, all other bearings, leather drive belts and shafts were oiled, checked and any necessary works carried to ensure they were safe to operate. However, where belts were assessed as worn but safe, these were left in place and they will be monitored and replaced if and when necessary for safety. Research was carried out regarding possible protective treatments for the ferrous metal tools, dies and machinery. This related to a large number of objects; approximately 15,000 dies and the same number of cutting and hand tools. Trials were carried out on selected items which were left in situ for the year of the building works to assess the effectiveness of the different treatments; the criteria were difficult: needing to be effective in high humidity levels; not be shiny or alter appearance; be easily applied in situ; reversible; be easily available and to have no health and safety concerns. Much thought was given when a comprehensive programme of treatment should be started. Ultimately the decision was taken to monitor and reassess after a year of small trials.

The decision not to treat the dies immediately was for a number of reasons; a treatment which satisfied all criteria had not yet been determined, there was concern regarding the amount of 'cleaning up' of the dies surface needed to make the treatments effective and ineffective treatments (due to the aggressive environment) had the potential to be an unnecessary expense. This approach had a risk associated, as once project money was withdrawn (all projects have to bid for new monies each financial year) the dies would remain untreated. It deterioration was then observed the project might struggle to raise the funds to treat the objects. Thankfully the 'traditional' system of lubricating dies and then placing a pressing of the die over the worked surface has proved to be surprisingly effective in reducing deterioration. Although the dies look very dusty and neglected, we have found the worked surfaces to generally be in good condition.

Consolidation (but no redecoration) of the most deteriorated surfaces was carried out, both to slow deterioration and to make maintenance of the building and machinery practical. Vulnerable plaster edges were treated, flaking paint and plaster surfaces consolidated and peeling wallpaper was re-adhered to give greater strength. However a pragmatic approach had to be adopted due to the number and scale of the deteriorated surfaces; with the potential treatment of walls and ceilings of over 50 rooms. In very friable areas the loosest areas were gently brushed down, before the remaining area was consolidated. There was a programme of dust removal in certain areas, for instance in corners where the dust sealing failed and white plaster dust had fallen onto a cluster of objects.

Alongside building works, attention was given to the two disassociated collections of silverware and archive. The silverware was removed from its newspaper wrappings, cleaned and installed in a custom built showroom with modern cases that replicated the originals (but with improved security and internal environments). Consideration was given to trying to refurbish the existing cases but the costs would have been greater than commissioning new cases and the environment still unlikely to be satisfactory. The extensive personal and business archive was removed to a new 'archive room', which had been re-plastered and painted and installed with dehumidifiers and archival racking. A number of the most significant items were cleaned and digitised to allow them to be accessed remotely if required. This had an initial cost but is likely to be significantly lower than continued conservation costs.

Following the completion of the project, the site is now open but does not have an agreed long-term strategy. The original objective was to hand over the site for a trust to run but to date, this has not been achieved. In the short term the site is administered by one EH staff member, with tours run by a team of volunteers. There is also the possibility of developing one of the houses as a business or residential arm of the property to help sustain the heritage element of the site. However in the current economic climate this idea is in abeyance but may be reconsidered in the future.

Future care and maintenance of the site will have to continue regardless of its long term future. The evidence provided by the collections 'risk and condition' survey combined with monitoring during the building works programme determined that the majority of the site should remain unheated. The building

is now water tight with good ventilation, which has mitigated the greatest risk to the collections. Relative humidity and temperature are monitored using a radio telemetric system and targeted condition surveys will be undertaken to check on the rate of deterioration of the metalwork.

JW Evans Silverware factory is significant cost project with low monetary return. Set against this is the very high value of the cultural and 'industrial history' contribution to the local area and the nation which gives visitors the experience of stepping into an untouched treasure. As an evocative industrial property, there was a strong sense of public ownership and widespread support, especially by local communities. Often during open days or tours, we would have visitors recounting stories of family members who had worked in the Birmingham Jewellery Quarter.

During the three years of the project we opened for 'Heritage Open Days' (a weekend of behind the scenes tours of properties not normally open to the public) and many visitors came back each year to see what works had been carried out. Interestingly a higher percentage of visitors were local, 'blue collar workers' in a younger age category than our typical visitor demographic. JW Evans is currently one of the few English Heritage properties predominantly run by volunteers (many of whom are local to the area and/or connected with the Jewellery Quarter). This helps demonstrate some of the intangible 'value' of such a site. We are reaching out to an under represented part of the public and it is ultimately the public who will lobby for heritage and its importance. Here we have a site where individuals are willing to give up their time and expertise freely in order to show others how much they value and care about this property and its contents. That is something you just can't put in a spreadsheet.